

SKILL-BASED HUMAN CAPITAL POTENTIAL DEVELOPMENT BASED ON THE COMMUNITY TOURISM INNOVATIVE LIFESTYLE

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Abstract

The research of “Skill-Based Human Capital Potential Development Based on the Community Tourism Innovative Lifestyle” was aimed to develop the skill-based human capital potential based on the community tourism innovative lifestyle and study the impact and guidelines for dynamic development and management based on the cultural capital of community tourism enterprise. The findings revealed that a structure of the community tourism innovative lifestyle had focused on managing tourism by the community, but it was still unsuccessful as it should be as their lodging services in almost all districts have not applied a concept of community tourism focusing on the truly local dining and resting such as the small hotels in Thale Noi area. The pilot community tourism development revealed that the mountain and forest areas had good potential in natural resources and atmosphere. In addition, a study of the impact and guidelines for dynamic development and management based on the cultural capital of community tourism enterprise revealed that; (1) There was a small impact as a gradual change, the community had adjusted to support the tourism for being the tourist attractions, (2) There was no impact to the occupation or lifestyle of people in the community as there was a small scale of tourist services, and (3) There was no migration, only the younger generation returned to the community during the COVID-19 pandemic in the last few months.

Introduction

The direction of driving Thai tourism in the future has to be developed for the stability, prosperity and sustainability. Stability is a competency of driving Thai tourism effectively through many crises from both national and international areas. Prosperity is a competency of earning and building economic stability for the country. Sustainability is a development responding to the tourist needs without affecting the society, environment and community. Consequently, the direction of driving Thai tourism has to respond to the tourism tendency in the global market with a larger scale of market share for quality and sustainable growth, creating tourism balance from the increase of income, expense, a number of rest days of tourists, and distribution of tourists and income to the community and local area in many regions including solving the urgent issues which are significant obstacles to tourism development in order to enhance the potential and competitive advantage for the entrepreneurs.

A conceptual framework of the next phase is the quality tourism development to develop Thailand as a quality leisure destination with six issues as follows; 1) enhancing higher tourist & stakeholder satisfaction by developing the quality and standard tourist attractions and services, developing the attractive, safe and clean landscape, developing the service-mind tourism entrepreneurs, and developing the accessible and comfortable tourism attractions by the infrastructure system development for the standard transportation covered the main routes and minor routes to the tourism attractions, 2) environment protection by considering service competency and tourism attractions restoration, 3) seasonality expansion for earning and

distributing more income to the tourism attractions, 4) income distribution for increasing options to the tourists, and employment to the local areas, 5) enhancing higher revenue and 6) sustainable growth (Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2015, online).

The 20-Year National Strategy (2017-2036) has a conceptual framework for building competitiveness focusing on developing the manufacturing and service sectors for sustainability, quality of life and higher income including the 12th National Economic and Social Development Plan (2017-2021) Strategy 3: Strengthening Economic and Sustainable Competitiveness, by a guideline for strengthening the business competitiveness of the service sector, and mission of the Ministry of Interior No.4: Strengthening the Community and Local Economy, by the participation of all sectors under the philosophy of sufficiency economy, the duties and responsibilities of the Department of Community Development in promoting the learning process and public participation, promoting and developing the stable local economy including strengthening the community and competency.

Currently, the government has a policy of reducing inequality of society that focuses on earning, prosperity and economic strength by allowing the private sector and people to participate with the public sector in order to achieve the vision, “Stability, Prosperity and Sustainability” which is consistent with OTOP Project in 2001 in all regions of the country, over the past 16 years, most of the community products had no competitiveness, had to sell products in different places, feeling unhappy, the income was not truly at the big group of people in the community but only one entrepreneur or small group causing the local economic development was not successful as it should be. Additionally, most of the tourism income which is the mainstream of the country was not at the local group but the private sectors such as hotels, restaurants, department stores and tour groups. In consequence, it needs a change from pushing OTOP products to the Demand Driven Local Economy by selling the community products made by attractive, wisdom, lifestyle, culture and creativity, and the lodging services with the obstacle of English skill. In terms of English skills, it is significant for the community enterprise in the service sector in Phatthalung Province as being the skilled workforce for communicating and educating technology. English skill will help to enhance knowledge, skill and competency updating with a change of global economy and society, but An Analysis on Communication Skills for Service Sectors among the Cultural and Language Diversity in the Community Enterprise of William (2007) revealed that the entrepreneurs and staff in community enterprises of the service sector still need foreign language skill development, especially English, in order to work in the tourism services effectively. Teaching English skills for community enterprises of the service sector was not successful and insufficient as it should be. Nevertheless, all family members still live together, no need to sell products in different places but the community as the tourist attraction by creating products and services including linking the community tourism routes by attractive and value for the tourists distributing to the community, making happiness, strengthening the community and being truly local economic development.

Phatthalung Province has defined a strategy to promote tourism in various forms; sea tourism, ecotourism, and historical and cultural tourism, etc., including promoting and supporting the development of products and services related to tourism such as One Tambon One Product (OTOP) in accordance with the era, but still conserving the identity of the community or local area. Phatthalung Province is located in the east of southern Thailand, away from Bangkok along the Asian route (National Highway 41) with a distance of approximately 858 kilometers, a total area of approximately 3,424.473 square kilometers and a population of 524,857. Nowadays, Phatthalung Province Administrative area is divided into 11 districts; Muang Phatthalung District, Khuan Khanun District, Khao Chaison District, Pak Phayun District, Kong Rha District, Ta Mhod District, Pa Bon District, Si Banphot District, Pa Phayom District, Bang Kaeo District and Srinakarin District. The Provincial emblem is Khao Ok Thalu where is a significant tourist attraction, with long stairs from the foothills to the cave and a hole in the middle for tourists to see the scenery of Phatthalung Province widely, But nowadays, it lacks development sustainable as the tourist attraction of the province. The vision of Phatthalung Province, "City of quality people, good environment, community strength, grow and prosper from the base of agriculture, culture, wisdom and sustainable conservative tourism." A community strength refers to a community where people have a simple way of life, live with the philosophy of a sufficiency economy, being employed, earn a sufficient income to live, have security guarantees, being safe in life and property, being protected by the law equally and fairly, having a human dignity, live in society happily, the culture and traditions of the community are managed strongly, and having the social and economic development value of the community. Phatthalung Province has defined five strategic issues focusing on strategic issues related to the community. The community strength is set as the first priority in the strategic issue of capacity building in the agricultural sector and downstream industries from agriculture, and community and local products.

The tourism of Phatthalung Province is one of twelve must-visit cities plus by the Tourism Authority of Thailand (TAT), the tourist attractions are Tham Khuha Sawan Temple, Phatthalung Governor’s Residence, Thale Noi, Wat Khian Bang Kaeo, Khao Chaison Hot

Spring & Cold Stream, Phriwan Waterfall, Khao Ok Thalu, Wat Wang, Saen Suk Lampam Beach and Khao Pu Khao Ya National Park. The community enterprises supporting the current tourism are Khuan Thon Pattana, Farmers' Housewives Group of Ban Thung Yao Pattana, Native Breed Cattle Farm Group in Land Reform Area of Ban Khuan Yuan Moo.9, Hom Thong, Mushroom Farm of Ban Khuan Yuan, Farmers' Housewives Group of Ban Khuan Thon, Phatthalung Curry Paste Network, Saving Group of Mae Khri Municipality, Agricultural Cooperatives of Tamot, and Farmers' Housewives Group of Plakpom Samakee. The well-known OTOPs are Sam Rasri Soap, coconut shell products, Sangyod Rice, Nang Talung craving, and Krajood products. All community enterprises and small enterprises have the potential of making products and services for the tourists, but it should be more improved the appropriate management to support the commercial airports in the future.

As the importance above, the researcher is interested in studying the Skill-Based Human Capital Potential Development Based on the Community Tourism Innovative Lifestyle, to develop the tourism management, language skill and service competency of people in the community. Creating happiness to pass on a friendly feeling to support community tourism as earning, distributing the tourist attractions for more options to the tourists, distributing career and income to the local areas, increasing cost per capita, and creating added value in the tourism products for sustainable growth balancing with the competency of each province.

Objective

1. To study the dynamic potential in tourism management suitable for Phatthalung Province
2. To study the impact and guidelines for dynamic development and management based on the cultural capital of community tourism enterprise.

Terminology definition

1. **Human capital potential development** refers to an improvement and a change of skills, knowledge, competency and personal qualities in Phatthalung Province.
2. **Skill** refers to expertise by keep practicing in various activities of people in Phatthalung Province.
3. **Tourism innovative lifestyle** refers to an experience of lifestyle, living culture, dining culture and community attraction in Phatthalung Province.
4. **Community of Phatthalung Province** refers to a group of people in 4 small areas; mountain, forest, field and sea areas in Phatthalung Province.
5. **Attitudes towards tourism tendency in Phatthalung Province** refers to an evaluation of feelings, behavioral tendency towards qualities and overall benefits of human capital skill development based on the community tourism innovative lifestyle or an idea arising from the behavioral tendency caused by satisfaction or dissatisfaction with something.
6. **Service and service provider** refers to entrepreneurs, community enterprises and tour service staff in Phatthalung Province.

Methodology

The researcher applied the qualitative research methodology with the processes and methods as follows;

1. A Study of Skill-Based Human Capital Potential Based on the Community Tourism Innovative Lifestyle in Phatthalung Province

1.1 Key informants

Data sources comprised of the secondary data from the relevant documents and researches, and the key informants comprised of; (1) five souvenir shop entrepreneurs and community enterprises, (2) five government staff in 4 areas; mountain, forest, field and sea areas in Phatthalung Province in order to gather the primary data of 4 programs.

1.2 Research instruments

Data was gathered by using (1) a mind map, to gather and categorize the relevant documents and researches for being a map of thinking, and (2) focus group interview and in-depth interview, to gather data from the key informants.

1.3 Data gathering

Data gathering comprised of (1) relevant documents and researches from the secondary data, (2) in-depth interview, and (3) focus group interview on skill-based human capital potential based on the community tourism innovative lifestyle in Phatthalung Province with the 40 key informants; (1) five entrepreneurs or community enterprises in the eastern areas (excluded from the group in Part 1), and (2) five customers.

1.4 Data analysis

Data from the secondary data, in-depth interview and focus group interview were analyzed by recording details and using the content analysis.

Results and Discussion

A study of the dynamic potential of tourism management suitable for Phatthalung Province

The distinct uniqueness of Phatthalung Province to attract the tourists is the location of mountain, forest, field and sea areas, which is rather more potential than other provinces. For the previous time, Phatthalung Province is located surrounding by rich nature as it is not a tourist attraction; there are no lodging services, improvement, creating uniqueness and identity, and tourism management. But nowadays, it starts the 2021 Provincial Strategies with a concept of Green Tourism by using SWOT Analysis and setting a goal of being a Province of the Sustainable Agriculture or Green Gold which the agriculture is like gold. In addition, tourism is supported more by the public and private sectors for being a tourist attraction for such the infrastructure development, career promotion for the community, and focusing on the interdependence among communities and large and small entrepreneurs in the tourism industry.

Projects or activities to support knowledge of local management (referred by a change of tourist behavioral tendency for more staying at the local community); innovative lifestyle tourism project, rural tourism focusing on managing tourism by the community, but it was still unsuccessful as it should be as their lodging services in almost all districts have not applied a concept of community tourism focusing on the truly local dining and resting such as the small hotels in Thale Noi area. The pilot community tourism development revealed that the mountain and forest areas had good potential in natural resources and atmosphere, which is consistent with the concept of (Ferrell, Hirt & Ferrell. 2014, p.232), product development is a process of idea screening, business analysis, and development for new products, with a large scale of investment for responding to the consumer needs in new innovative products.

A study of the impact and guidelines for dynamic development and management based on the cultural capital of community tourism enterprise

1. There was a small impact as a gradual change, the community had adjusted to support the tourism for being the tourist attractions.
2. There was no impact to the occupation or lifestyle of people in the community as there was a small scale of tourist services.
3. There was no migration, only the younger generation returned to the community during the COVID-19 pandemic in the last few months.

Conclusion and Suggestion

1. Guiding tourists on many tourist attractions as it could be always relied on the big entrepreneurs.
2. Promoting direct tourist spots and linking the big spots to small spots of each area focusing on public relations or providing information of various tourist attractions for tourists.
3. As the public sectors and village head disagreed with the concept of the community fund, people in the community claimed their rights by closing the broadcast station and multipurpose area, and formed their group for meeting without using the broadcast station. After their group was strengthened, it was more supported by the public sectors such as the vice-governor and sheriff

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